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**A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MOTORISED CARGO TRICYCLE
CONNECTING ROD USING ABAQUS**

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ABSTRACT

This report outlines systematic modeling and comparative analysis of connecting rod of a motorized cargo tricycle (popularly referred to as motor king in the northern part of Ghana and as Aboboyaa in the south). Two different designs, solid and hollow shank connecting rods, made from three different alloying materials (AA 6061, Ti - 5Al - 2.5Sn and AISI 1045) were modeled and analyzed using the finite element analysis (F.E.A) software (ABACUS CAE / 2022 Learning Edition). The crank end of the connecting rod was constrained, and a load of 1371 kN was applied at the piston end pointing south. After analysis, results showed that the stress induced in the piston end was higher than the one induced on the crank end. This was attributed to the colour red at the piston end and the colour blue at the crank end. Titanium alloy had the least stress value of 5000 pa for the solid shank followed by AA6061 alloy with a value of 9000 pa and AISI 1045 was the highest with a stress value of 13000 pa, also, for the hollow shank titanium had the least stress value of 3900 pa followed by AA 6061 of 41000 pa with the greatest value of stress still being AISI 1045 having a value of 7000 pa. Elastic strain and deformations analysis showed that titanium alloy was the most resilient showing a max elastic strain of 19 for the solid shank and 23 for the hollow shank and deformation amount of 16 m for solid and 18 m for hollow shank. AISI 1045 was least resilient showing maximum elastic strain of 70 for solid and 75 for hollow and total deformation of 26 m for solid and 30 m for hollow. In terms of design, the solid shank connecting rod showed the least deformation irrespective of material used. For example AA 6061 deformed by 20 m, titanium by 16 m and AISI 1045 by 26m.

Keywords: Abaqus; Connecting rod; Elastic Strain; Deformation; Von – Misses stress.

1. INTRODUCTION

A motorized cargo tricycle also referred to as the ‘motor king’ in the Upper East Region of Ghana is a three-wheeled vehicle based on the same technology as a motorcycle, and operates on the principle of two stroke cycle engine. It is mostly used in carry goods from remote villages to market centers and for carrying passenger in areas where there is no access to vehicles or where the roads are not motorable. Due to the nature of work that the operators of this tricycle have to do, they usually engage in overloading without considering the maximum load limit of these machines and thereby causing breakages to some engine components as well as exceeding the safe working stresses of vital components such as the crank shaft and the connecting rods.

The function of the connection rod is to transfer thrust in either direction between the piston and the crankpin. It is usually about twice as long as the stroke of the engine and is subjected to forces which try to bend, stretch and compress it. It is usually of H shaped cross section to resist these forces and it is either made of an alloy steel forging, an aluminum alloy forging of equivalent strength but lighter in weight or is made of titanium [1]. Therefore, a connecting rod must be capable of transmitting axial tension, axial compression, and bending stresses caused by the thrust and pull on the piston and by Centrifugal force [2]. Also, the pin that connects the connecting rod to the piston called the piston pin or gudgeon pin gets a lot of wear, and when this pin snaps, the connecting rod is no longer connected to the piston and this results in catastrophic engine failure and the

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[55]

connecting rod goes through the engine block or the crankshaft is bent but for some engines it just causes a dramatic loss of power [3]. According to [4], the connecting rod is subjected to a complex state of loading.

In a study by [5], they carried out stress analysis on connecting rod of a motor vehicle and their main objective was to determine stresses in the existing connecting rod, which are in different cross-section. The failures of existing design suggest the minimum design changes in the existing connecting rod.

The fatigue analysis of connecting rod using finite element analysis to explore weight and cost reduction opportunities was performed by [6], it was observed that every vehicle that uses an internal combustion engine requires at least one connecting rod depending upon the number of cylinders in the engine. Due to its large volume production, it is only logical that optimization of the connecting rod for its weight or volume will result in large-scale savings. It can also achieve the objective of reducing the weight of the engine component, thus reducing inertia loads, reducing engine weight and improving engine performance and fuel economy.

2. OBJECTIVE

The frequent break down of motorized cargo tricycle connecting rod couple with the rising cost of spare parts for these machines has led people to search for ways to reduce the occurrence of these problem and to help minimize production and maintenance cost of machine parts in order to meet their financial needs and to help them live a productive life to contribute to the economic growth of countries like Ghana. It is in view of these that the researcher intends to analyzed two different designs of a motorized cargo tricycle connecting rod of three different materials to determine the Von – Mises stress, rate of deformation and elastic strain

The specific objectives of the project include:

- To model two different designs of motorize cargo tricycle connecting rod using ABAQUS/CAE 2022 learning edition.
- To perform static structure analysis on the two designs using three different materials. (AA 6061 Aluminum Alloy, Ti - 5Al - 2.5Sn Titanium Alloy and AISI 1045 Steel Alloy)
- To determine which of the materials used in the design of the connecting rod is more suitable for use in Motorized Cargo Tricycles

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Materials Used

Three different types of materials which are mostly used in connecting rod manufacture were used for the analysis and these are;

3.1.1 Aluminum alloy (AA 6061)

This material consisting of the following alloying composition; aluminum (Al), 95.85 – 98.56 %, magnesium (Mg), 0.8 - 1.2 %, silicon (Si) 0.4 - 0.8%, iron (Fe), 0.00 – 0.7, copper (Cu), 0.15 - 0.40%, chromium (Cr), 0.04 – 0.35 %, zinc (Zn), 0.00 – 0.25, titanium (Ti), 0.00 – 0.25 and manganese (Mn), 0.0 – 0.15. The AA 6061 aluminum alloy is heat treatable, easily formed, weld- able, and is good at resisting corrosion. [7] .

3.1.2 Titanium alloy

Titanium alloy also known as Ti - 5Al - 2.5Sn and contains; aluminum (Al), 5 % , tin (Sn) 2.5 %, vanadium (V), 4%, iron (Fe), 0.25%, oxygen (O), 0.2% and titanium 88.05%. [8].

3.1.3 AISI 1045 steel alloy

AISI 1045 steel alloy made of; carbon (C), 0.43 – 0.50 %, manganese (Mn), 0.60 – 0.90 %, Sulphur (S), 0.05 %, phosphorous (P), 0.04 %, and iron (Fe), 98.51%. The AISI 1045 steel alloy is made to function in areas requiring greater strength and hardness. This steel possesses excellent size accuracy, concentricity, and straightness which together enable it to minimize wear in high-speed applications. [9].

3.2 Methods

Solid Works was used to develop the geometry, and subsequently ABACUS CAE 2022 Learning Edition was utilized to simulate and analyze the various connecting rod designs.

4. DESIGN

Design Specification of the Connecting Rod

Design specification is a list of criteria that a product needs to address and it can be written when more facts are known about the design and the information that needs to be found through research in order to help produce early design solutions and improvements. It contains detailed document that provides a list of points regarding the product or process which include the required dimensions, environmental factors, ergonomic factors, aesthetic factors and maintenance that will be needed. It may also give specific examples of how the design should be executed, helping others to work properly or serve as a guideline for what the person should do.

Table 1: Design specification of the connecting rod made of all three materials

	AA 6061 ALUMINUM ALLOY	TITANIUM ALLOY	AISI 1045 STEEL ALLOY
Description	Value	Value	Value
Speed of Engine	14,000 p.m.	14,000 r.p.m	14,000 r.p.m
Bore Diameter	63 mm	63 mm	63 mm
Mass of reciprocating parts	0.381 kg	0.381 kg	0.381 kg
Factor of safety	2	2	2
Young's modulus	68.9 x e 10 ⁹ mPa	9.6 x e 10 mPa	200 e 9 mPa
Poisson's ratio	0.3	0.36	0.29
Mass Density	2700 kg/m ³	4620 kg/m ³	7870 kg/m ³
Yield Strength	670 mpa	800 Mpa	686 mpa
Wall pressure for piston rings	0.17 Pa	0.17 Pa	0.17 Pa
Number of rings	3	3	3
Coefficient of friction	0.05	0.05	0.05
Explosion pressure	2.15 Pa	2.15 Pa	2.15 Pa
Length of rod	70 mm	70 mm	70 mm
Piston pin diameter	13 mm	13 mm	13 mm
Crank pin diameter	35 mm	35 mm	35 mm

4.2 Forces Acting on the Connecting Rod

According to [10], the forces that acts on an engine connecting rod as it moves in the cylinder consist of the following:

- Force due to inertia of the connecting rod and reciprocating mass.
- Force due to friction of the piston rings and the cylinder wall.
- Force on the piston due to gas pressure.

4.2.1 Force Calculations.

- **Force due to inertial of connecting rod and reciprocating mass (Fi).**

According to [11], inertia is the sluggishness or reluctance of a body to motion or to change of motion and is largely dependent on the mass of the body.

$$F_i = \frac{M \times \omega^2 \times r \times (\cos\theta + (r \cos\theta))}{L} \quad (i).$$

Where;

M= Mass of reciprocating parts.

ω = angular revolution

r = big end / crank pin radius

L = length of connecting rod.

θ = angle formed when piston is at top dead centre

$$F_i = \frac{0.381 \times (2 \times 3.142 \times 14000)^2 \times 17.5 \times (\cos 0 + (17.5 \cos 0))}{70} = 1363.845 \text{ kN}$$

- **Force due to friction of the piston rings and the cylinder wall (Ff).**

Friction is the resistance to relative motion which exists between two surfaces in contact. It may be undesirable as in the case between the piston rings and the cylinder wall, where it absorbs energy, generates heat and causes wear. [12]

$$F_f = h \times \pi \times d \times n \times P_r \times \mu \quad (ii)$$

Where;

- F_f = frictional force
- h = length of stroke = 40 mm
- π = 3.142
- d = bore diameter = 63 mm
- n = number of rings = 3
- P_r = wall pressure of piston ring = 0.17 Pa
- μ = coefficient of friction = 0.05

$$\therefore F_f = 40 \times 3.142 \times 63 \times 3 \times 0.17 \times 0.05 = 201.9 \text{ N}$$

- Force due to gas pressure (F_g)

$$\text{Pressure (P)} = \frac{\text{Force (Fg)}}{\text{Area (A)}} \quad (iii).$$

$$\text{Force (Fg)} = \text{Pressure (P)} \times \text{Area (A)}$$

$$\text{but area (A)} = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} \text{ where d is the cylinder bore diameter}$$

$$\therefore F_g = P \times A = 2.15 \times \frac{\pi 63^2}{4} = 6702.95 \text{ N}$$

- Force acting on piston (F)

This is the sum of all the force;

$$F = F_i + F_f + F_g \quad (iv)$$

$$F = 1363845 + 201.9 + 6702.95 = 1370749.85 \text{ N} = 1370.75 \text{ kN}$$

- Force acting on connecting rod (F_c).

$$F_c = \frac{F}{\cos \beta} \quad (v)$$

$$= \frac{1370.75}{\cos 0} = 1370.75 \text{ kN} \quad (\text{Since } \beta = 0, \text{ at top dead centre})$$

4.3 Modeling of the Connecting Rods.

A typical simulation consists of setting up the model and the loads applied to it and then solving for the model's response to the loads depending on the design nodes and elements.

Figure.1: Design of solid shank Connecting Rod

Figure .2: Modeling of solid shank Connecting Rod.

Figure 3: Design of hollow shank Connecting Rod

Figure 4: Modeling of hollow shank Connecting rod

4.3.1 Applying Boundary Condition to the two different modeled Connecting Rods

Prescribed conditions, such as loads and boundary conditions are step dependent, which means that you must specify the step or steps in which they become active. In structural analysis of the connecting rod, boundary conditions were applied to those regions of the model where the displacement and or rotation are known. Such regions may be constrain to remain fixed (ie have zero displacement during the simulation and in this modeled connecting rod the big end or the crank pin portion of the connecting rod is constrained completely and thus cannot move in any direction. The small end portion of the connecting rod is however not fixed and it is free to move in the vertical direction. The direction in which motion is possible is called degree of freedom (dof).

Figure 5: Boundary condition applied to the solid shank connecting rod

Figure 6: Boundary condition applied to the hollow shank connecting rod.

4.3.2 Applying the Load to the modeled Connecting Rods

Now that the model has been constrained, the load will then have to be applied and in this case a concentrated load of 1371 kN which is equal to the force acting on the connecting rod is applied at the small end portion of the connecting rod and was applied downwards as shown in the figure below.

Figure7: Applied load to the solid shank connecting rod

Figure 8: Applied load to the hollow shank connecting rod.

4.4 Meshing the Modelled Connecting Rods.

The basis of finite element analysis (F.E.A) relies on the decomposition of the domain into a finite number of sub domains (elements) for which the systematic approximate solutions are constructed by applying the variation or weighted residual method. In effect, F.E.A reduces the problem to that of a finite number of unknowns by dividing the domains into elements and by expressing the unknown field variable in terms of the assumed approximating function within each element. These functions (also called interpolation functions) are defined in terms of the values of the field variables at specific points, referred to as nodes. Nodes are usually located along the element boundaries and are connected to the adjacent elements. A meshing size of 4 mm is what was settled on and used because from a meshing size of 5 mm downwards there was no change in the values of the analysis that was performed.

Figure 9: Meshing of the solid shank connecting rod

Figure10: Meshing of the hollow shank connecting rod

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Analysis of two different designs (solid and hollow shank) of motorized cargo try cycle connecting rods made of three different materials (AA 6061 Aluminum Alloy, Titanium Alloy and AISI 1045 Steel) have been carried out and at the end von misses stress, deformation and elastic strain was analyzed using finite element analysis method or the Abaqus software and the results are as follows;

5.1 Von Misses Stress Analysis.

The von Misses stress is often used in determining whether a ductile metal will yield or fracture when subjected to a complex loading condition. The von Misses yield criterion states that if the von misses stress of a material under load is equal or greater than the yield limit of the same material under simple tension then the material will yield or fracture. Therefore, if in the entire model Von Misses stresses are lower than yield strength then the material is fit for the purpose [13]. The equivalent Von- Misses stress value of the connecting rod is determined by using the software and the value obtained varying from the maximum von misses stress occurring at the small end portion of the connecting rod and is indicated by the colour red followed by yellow and green colours with the minimum stress occurring at the portion with blue colour as shown in the figures below.

Figure 11: Von- Mises stress analysis for solid shank connecting rod made of AA 6061 steel

Figure12: Von- Mises stress analysis for hollow shank connecting rod made of AA 6061 steel

Figure 13: Von- Mises stress analysis for solid shank connecting rod made of Titanium alloy

Figure 14: Von- Mises stress analysis for hollow shank connecting rod made of Titanium alloy

Figure 15: Von- Mises stress analysis for solid shank connecting rod made of AISI 1045 Steel Alloy material

Figure 16: Von- Mises stress analysis for hollow shank connecting rod made of AISI 1045 Steel Alloy material.

Table 2: Von Misses Stress

SOLID SHANK			HOLLOW SHANK		
AA 6061 ALLOY (pa)	TITANIUM ALLOY (pa)	AISI 1045 STEEL (pa)	AA 6061 ALLOY (pa)	TITANIUM ALLOY (pa)	AISI 1045 STEEL (pa)
4250	4223	4143	4197	3562	6898
3850	3873	3799	3849	3266	6324
3543	3522	3455	3500	2970	5750
3190	3171	3112	3152	2674	5175
2837	2821	2768	2803	2378	4601
2483	2470	2424	2455	2082	4027
2130	2119	2080	2106	1787	3452
1777	1769	1736	1757	1491	2878
1423	1418	1393	1409	1195	2304
1070	1067	1049	1060	898.9	1729
716.5	716.8	705.0	711.9	603.0	1155
363.2	366.1	361.2	363.3	307.1	580.8
9.818	15.45	17.36	14.79	11.22	6.455

Figure 17: Stress values for Solid Shank connecting rods.

Figure 18: Stress values for Hollow Shank connecting rods

From figure 11 to figure 16 it can be seen that the stress induced in the piston end of the connecting rod with the red colour was much greater than the stress induced at the crank pin end of the connecting rod which is coloured blue and shows that the piston end was prone to fracture as compared to the big end and comparing it with the yield strength of the three materials used for the analysis, they are all fit for purpose.

Table 2 and Figure 17 and 18 gives the results for both solid and hollow shank connecting rods made of the three different materials and from the graph it can be seen that titanium alloy is the strongest and therefore is better fit for purpose than the other two materials.

5.2 Elastic Strain (EE) Analysis

Elastic strain is a form of deformation that is fully recovered upon removal of the applied load and depends on the density of interatomic bonds in the material. When a material is stressed there is a resulting strain and if the stress is low then the strain will be what is termed elastic strain. This type of strain is caused by stretching of the bonds in the material. According to [14], Elastic strain is a widely used parameter to control and modify the electrical, optical, and magnetic properties of crystalline solid-state materials. It has a large impact on device performance and enables adjusting of materials functionality

Many metals in the elastic region have a resulting strain that is proportional to the tensile load when the applied tensile load is small. Mathematically, this can be written as $\sigma = E \epsilon_e$, and more generally is known as a form of Hooke's law. (Elastic Strain: $\epsilon_e = \sigma/E$). [15].

5.2.1 Elastic Strain Analysis for Solid Shank Connecting Rods:

Elastic strain (EE) analysis for the solid shank design of the connecting rods made of AA6061 aluminum alloy, titanium alloy and AISI 1045 steel alloy is as shown below;

Figure 19: Elastic Strain analysis for solid shank AA 6061 Aluminium Alloy

Figure 20: Elastic Strain analysis for solid shank Titanium Alloy

Figure 21: Elastic Strain analysis for solid shank AISI 1045 Steel Alloy

5.2.2 Elastic Strain analysis for Hollow Shank Connecting Rods

Elastic strain (EE) analysis of the hollow shank design of connecting rods made of AA6061 aluminum alloy, titanium alloy and AISI 1045 steel alloy as carried out is as shown below;

Figure 22: Elastic Strain analysis for hollow shank AA 6061 Aluminum Alloy

Figure 23: Elastic Strain analysis for hollow shank Titanium Alloy.

Figure 24: Elastic Strain analysis for hollow shank AISI 1045 STEEL ALLOY.

Table 3: Elastic Strain Analysis (EE)

SOLID SHANK			HOLLOW SHANK		
AA 6061 ALLOY	TITANIUM ALLOY	AISI 1045 STEEL	AA 6061 ALLOY	TITANIUM ALLOY	AISI 1045 STEEL
45	19	70	50	23	75
20	17	66	22	17	67
18	16	60	20	16	61
17	14	54	18	14	55
15	13	48	16	13	49
13	11	42	14	11	43
11	10	36	12	10	37
9	8	30	10	8	31
7	6	24	8	6	25
6	5	18	6	5	18
4	3	12	4	3	12
2	2	6	0	0	0

Figure25: Elastic Strain (EE) Analysis for solid and hollow shank connecting rods

From figure 25, it can be seen that AISI 1045 has the highest amount of elastic strain followed by AA 6061 Aluminum Alloy with Titanium having the least amount of elastic strain for both solid and hollow shanks thereby making titanium the best material among the three.

5.3 Deformation Analysis.

Deformation refers to the change in shape or size of an object depending on the type of material, size and geometry of the object, and the load applied [16]. The deformation is said to be elastic if the material returns to its original shape and size upon removal of the applied load. On the other hand, it is referred to as inelastic or plastic deformation if the application of the load results in a permanent change in the shape of the object, in other words if it doesn't return to its original shape and size even if the load is no longer being applied to it. [17]. For the connecting rod deformation, the two different designs were analyzed using the F.E.A software and the results is as shown in the figures below.

5.3.1 Deformation Analysis for solid shank connecting rod.

The deformation analysis of the solid shank design of the connecting rods made of AA6061 aluminum alloy, titanium alloy and AISI 1045 steel alloy is as shown below;

Figure 27: Deformation of solid shank connecting rod made of AA 6061 steel

Figure 28: Deformation of the solid shank connecting rod made of Titanium Alloy.

Figure 29: Deformation of the solid shank connecting rod made of AISI 1045 Steel Alloy

5.3.2 Deformation Analysis for hollow shank connecting rod.

The deformation analysis of the hollow shank design of the connecting rods made of AA6061 aluminum alloy, titanium alloy and AISI 1045 steel alloy is as shown below.

Figure: 30: Deformation of the hollow shank connecting rod made of AA 6061 Steel.

Figure 31: Deformation of the hollow shank connecting rod made of Titanium alloy

Figure 32: Deformation of the hollow shank connecting rod made of AISI 1045 Steel Alloy

Table 4: Rate of Deformation

MATERIAL	SOLID SHANK	HOLLOW SHANK
AA 6061 ALLOY	20 m	25 m
TITANIUM ALLOY	16 m	18 m
AISI 1045	26 m	30 m

Figure 23: Deformation for both hollow and solid shank connecting rods

As shown in table 4 and figure 23, it can be seen that even though the two designs of the connecting rods (solid and hollow shanks) are made of the same materials (i.e.; AA 6061, Titanium Alloy or AISI 1045 Alloy Steel) their rate of deformation varies, and this is evident that titanium alloy had the least deformation followed by AA6061, while AISI 1045 was the most deformed material.

6. CONCLUSION

Two different designs (Solid Shank and Hollow Shank) of motorized cargo tricycle connecting rod made of three different alloying materials (Aluminum Alloy {AA 6061}, Titanium Alloy {Ti - 5Al} and Steel Alloy {AISI 1045}) has been designed, modelled and analyzed using the Finite Element Analysis (F.E.A) software (ABACUS CAE 2022 Learning Edition). A load of 1371 kN was applied at the small end of the connecting rod of each design and was made to act downwards while the big end was constrained.

The Von Misses stress analysis carried out as shown in figure 17 and 18, shows that titanium alloy had the least stress value than the other two materials and therefore is considered the strongest. For Elastic strain and deformations analysis it is concluded that titanium alloy was the most resilient showing a maximum elastic strain of 19 for the solid shank and 23 for the hollow shank and deformation amount of 16 m for solid and 18 m for hollow shank. AISI 1045 was least resilient showing maximum elastic strain of 70 for solid and 75 for hollow and total deformation of 26 m for solid and 30 m for hollow. In terms of design, it is concluded that solid shank connecting rod made of titanium alloy is the best as it showed the least deformation, least stress and the least elastic strain among the two designs.

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